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Early Childhood Care and Education in Malaysia and Nigeria: A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The quality of life of a people and by implications the national development of states can be improved through comparative pedagogy especially comparative studies of educational systems of states. Using the philosophical methodology and theoretically guided by social constructivism, this study focuses on the comparison of early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria, two countries that recognize the fundamental and foundational necessity of early childhood care and education in their national developments. The paper identified similarities and differences in the commitment of the two states towards early childhood care and education and at the same time passes positive remarks in the efforts of Malaysia to transition to higher grounds on the development index through insightful policies and genuine commitment to early childhood care and education while acknowledging Nigeria as a country that pays lip services to serious issues of national concern including early childhood care and education. The paper make recommendations, part of which is that Malaysia should continue to provide incentives to private investors and increase its participation in early childhood care and education and Nigeria should demonstrate genuine commitment to promoting the training of qualified preprimary teachers, participate directly as well as provide incentives to private investors in early childhood care and education who provide essential service that the state should provide among others.

Keywords: Early childhood care and education, Malaysia, Nigeria, Comparative analysis.

INTRODUCTION

One value which states share in common without regard to their various levels of developmental sophistication, level of civility or level of backwardness is the recognition and acknowledgement of the fact that investment in human capital development or human capacity building is the foundation of development in all its ramifications. Human capital development or human capacity building can take many forms but the form that is more superlative in generating dividends that generate positive multiplier effects in terms of translating changes into reality, forming, reforming and transforming the individual and the society along lines where the individual becomes more productive and more functional for himself in particular and humanity generally, and where the society becomes more equitable, equal and producing promising signs with sustainable norms that can give all humanity a sense of belonging is that which is routed through education.

Education plays crucial and pivotal roles in the life of individuals and the sustainable growth and development of the state and such critical and crucial roles education plays in the life of individuals and the state makes education one social provision which every responsible state must provide for the citizens

(Shively, 2005). At the international levels, education continues to be the focus and central point of many deliberations, conventions, conferences, and workshops that involve renowned world leaders and many celebrated and respected think-tanks so much that education is looked upon presently and, in the future, to provide answers and solutions to present and future problems of man and the society.

The high esteem in which the global community holds education derives from the fact that education can be used to bring about all forms of social reforms, social transformations and social reengineering across all epistemological frontiers and space that can take human kind to the next level of desirable developments. It is a fact that cannot be doubted that states that have made their marks in food production and food sufficiency (food security), environmental protection, states that have diplomatically, politically, socially, economically, scientifically and technologically being on track or that have made their marks are those states that have transitioned and repositioned their education and at the same time made investments in human capital development their topmost priorities. The dividends such states derive from education can be so comprehensive and inclusive so much that education enables and empowers citizens in such states with the capacity for acquiring skills and creative procedures for initiating creative thoughts that have potentials to lay foundations for robust economic, political, scientific and technological breakthroughs, develop in the citizens a nationalistic and patriotic consciousness for triggering a revolution in thinking that can result in sustainable management, exploitation and exploration of the natural resources of the environment as well as develop a corresponding behavioural disposition that can be supportive of harmonious and cordial relationships between individuals and fellow individuals, institutions and institutions, nations and nations where the promotion of justice and the consideration of each other's mutual interests can become norms.

The importance of education in transforming individuals and states in directions such individuals and states want to go has made many individuals and states across the globe to adopt education as the navigating radar for their development. In the spirit of adopting education as a navigating radar, Nigeria and Nigerians have embraced education as an instrument par excellence for national development and accordingly Nigeria emphatically notes that;

Education shall continue to be highly rooted in the national development plans because education is the most important instrument of change, any fundamental change in the intellectual and social outlook of any society has to be preceded by an educational revolution (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004:8)

The above is revealing and part of what it reveals is that the education industry globally is a hotbed of ideas and a flashpoint where there is so much desire for change particularly the desire to increase and expand access to it in addition to making education reflect the contemporary realities of the time in which it is provided to the people. The nature and manner of change in education is one that occurs in split seconds and in a manner that new ideas, new policies and new directions keep springing up so much that old practices are dropped and new ones are integrated and accommodated and in these orgies of changes in education, already initiated changes become obsolete before such changes are implemented. New ideas, new philosophies, new policies, and new directions that are in vogue and correspondingly the trending paradigm in education across the globe recognizes, acknowledges and aligns with contemporary realities that "education should be provided to the young ones prior to their entering primary school as a matter of right, equality and national development (Nwaokugha & Nwogu, 2024:61).

The most influential global decision on education that has helped to conscientize states to embrace education as their beacon of hope for their national development is the recognition of education as a human right by the United Nations. A human rights is a right which every human being, irrespective of age, sex, tribe, nationality, social economic status, status of birth etc is entitled to enjoy as a right, or a conglomerate of rights in which one must not be denied of, as any attempt to deny any one of such rights automatically means that such a person who has been denied such a right has been impaired and correspondingly may not maximally perform his social, cultural, economic and political functions effectively. The recognition of education as a human right by the United Nations confers on education the

status of a natural provision, which every citizen must receive and, on this basis, education serves what Nwaokugha and Nwogu (2024:61) call:

A threshold and basic entry point for the citizens' empowerment and the acquisition of the fundamentals for effective, rational, critical, analytic and reflective thinking, development of ability to make choices or choose between alternatives and more pointedly the acquisition of skills that can enable citizens to take active part in the cultural social, civil, political and democratic processes of their state.

The recognition and embrace of education as a human right by the global community is heartwarming but more heartwarming in the recognition of education as a human right is the receptivity in which education as a human right has been extended to early childhood care and education, that is, provision of education to young ones within the age bracket of 0-5 years or more, depending on the state across the globe. Many countries of the world have robust early childhood care and education programmes and many countries of the world equally do not have robust early childhood care and education programmes. In fact, those countries that may not have robust early childhood care and education programmes may be mere beginners in matters that border on early childhood care and education.

Interestingly, on any side of the divide any country finds itself, there are rooms to explore robust opportunities that exist in early childhood care and educational provisions especially the type of opportunity where countries that have robust and vibrant early childhood care and education programmes take advantage of their advanced profile and status in early childhood care and education to create rooms for further improvements in their early childhood education programmes as well as chart roadmaps for their national development. On the other hand, those countries where early childhood care and education programmes are non-existent or are merely beginning can copy, borrow ideas or model their own on ideas and structures of those countries that have a long history of vibrant and robust early childhood care and education programmes for the growth and sustainable development of early childhood care and education in their own country. What the foregoing reveals is that there can be rooms for comparative studies or analyses of early childhood care and education in any two countries of a scholar's choice. Upon this awareness and clarification, this study focuses on a comparative analysis of early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria. This study in all honesty and sincerity can be significant in a number of ways. The study can sensitize and conscientize scholars and researchers into developing skills on what to look out for in educational policies and programmes that have global outlook and focus across countries and through this way establish country or countries whose educational practices align with global best practices and country or countries whose educational practices did not align with global best practices. The study can be significant in that it can stimulate in scholars and researchers the curiosity and zeal to contribute to the growth of knowledge and by extension the growth of humanity. This position is taken because the study is a sure bet for sharpening researchers' and scholars' investigative skills. The study has the potentials to open up new unexplored epistemological frontiers and structural territories which states that have robust and vibrant history of early childhood care and education can still explore to further strengthen and maintain their stronghold on early childhood care and education. On the other hand, the study can also be a trigger for the modification and upgrading of practices in early childhood care and education institution especially in states where early childhood care and education is yet to record progress or is yet to have a stronghold. The study can be supportive of the thesis that knowledge and by implication human-kind can develop and survive better through mutual borrowing of ideas and adapting such ideas to the needs of the individuals and their states.

The theoretical framework upon which this study is based is social constructivism, which is also called social constructionism. Social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction aligns properly with qualitative or philosophical research and as a theory of knowledge construction, it is hinged on the premise that "Knowledge is not mechanically acquired but constructed with the constraints and offerings of the learning environment (Liu & Matthew, 2005:387). The above position is reechoed by Mogashoa

(2014) who writes that human beings are key in the generation of knowledge and meaning and it is correct to say that the foundation in which knowledge and meaning owe their roots is dependent on the degree of interactions that people hold. This means that the ideas and experiences of individuals who are involved in the process of interaction counts in the generation and construction of knowledge. This is revealing and part of what it reveals is that knowledge develops or is established through the actions and activities of man. In fact, Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:167) are correct when they write that social constructivism upholds that individuals make meaning and construct knowledge via their own skills, ideas and daily experiences through dialogue, interaction and communication with other members of the society.

Constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is unique and its uniqueness derives from its dominance in what happens in the generation and construction of knowledge especially between 1980s and 1990s over the years, its recognition both as a paradigm and a theory (Fosnot, 1996), its emphasis on learners' active participation in the process of knowledge construction and generation on one hand and the recognition that learning by nature is a social process that may be positively enhanced or negatively affected by activities and actions in the social environment. The recognition that learners' active participation in the process of knowledge construction and generation is crucial has introduced and triggered some pedagogical and epistemological revolutions, reengineering and awareness about constructivism, which on its own has become a popular concept, so popular that it has become a buzz word in school education and teacher training in the western world (Liu & Matthew, 2005). As a way of promoting learners' active participation, which is a fundamental requirement in a constructivist and constructivism dominated epistemological paradigm shift, teacher education institutions now pattern and structure their instructions in ways where priority is given to educating learners to demonstrate a sense of commitment towards breaking new frontiers of knowledge, to show a sense of commitment towards solving problems and responding to the demand of an ever-changing complex society, to demonstrate a desire for collaboration with others, possibly on the premise that epistemological frontiers and barriers can be easily broken for better human advancement when two or more persons harmoniously and cooperatively work together and lastly educating learners in a regime where constructivism is the norm and guiding paradigm must prioritize developing in the learners the ability and capacity to think creatively and critically.

The foregoing makes constructivism a popular theory of knowledge construction and its popularity has given rise to many variations of the concept, namely cognitive or personal constructivism, also called radical constructivism and social constructivism, and also called realist constructivism. Cognitive or personal (radical constructivism) upholds the idea that knowledge is individually constructed. What this translates into is that the development or evolution of knowledge is the critical or creative initiative and endeavour of an individual or a group that come together for the attainment of one epistemological belief and on the basis of this, advocates of cognitive or radical constructivism make case for the promotion of active engagement and active participation of the learner in the learning process or what Liu and Matthew (2005:388) call learner-centered and discovery oriented learning process while social or realist constructivism upholds the idea that social environment plays the most critical and crucial role in knowledge construction. One can say it with all amount of seriousness that the two positions above are central and critical in the development of knowledge in any institution and society.

The methodology adopted in this study is purely qualitative or philosophical and it is unique due to its robust reliance on what Angadi (2019) calls "collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other type of research". In the words of Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:11)

Qualitative philosophical research is exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational setting. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data such as interviews, observations, case studies and document analyses. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore

meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena.

Qualitative or philosophical research dwells so much on analysis, reflection, rigour of thought that prioritizes meaningfulness, semantic clarity and the development of skills that can lead to informed decisions that are capable of resolving any issues that are the focus of any philosophical endeavour. Lastly qualitative or philosophical research incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription, also called normative approach.

According to Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:4), speculation as a method of philosophical research invokes a meaning that revolves around “a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of a philosophical discourse. Scholars and researchers who rely on speculation for their studies do so by robustly building up ideas and carefully, sequentially, systematically and logically show how one idea is logically and systematically related to other ideas in the whole system of ideas (Nwaokugha & Keri-Frank, 2023:39). Speculation is key to any effective and successful philosophical research and why this is so is that speculation serves and stimulates curiosity in individuals and this is the foundation upon which some scholars and researchers simply describe it as a provocateur, a guide for improving performance and actions in the in the future (Nwaokugha & Nwogu, 2024:63), as it has potential to provide man and his institution with what Taggart (2012) calls higher order consolation and a kind of philosophy of action that serves as a guide for public philosophy. It has to be pointed out that the continuous relevance and reliance on speculation hinges on what Nwaokugha and Nwogu (2024:63) call:

Man’s innate desire and curiosity to know especially realities that continuously exert influence on man and his institution, yet lack definite universal explanation, so attempt to know, explain and understand reality are at the centre or heart of speculation and this lends credence to the age long saying that people speculate in order to know and logically the more people speculate on a particular subject matter, the more they are likely to break epistemological frontiers concerning the subject matter so far they speculate upon.

To this end, speculation becomes the first point of call people resort to when they are faced with scenarios and experiences that are strange or that they cannot easily comprehend. This is why subject matters that fall within the frame of reference of axiology, ranging from ethics, social philosophy, aesthetics, political philosophy and topics that are the focus and preoccupation of metaphysics are phenomenally attractive to speculation. It must be pointed out that one denominator which subject matters that are attractive to speculation share in common is their ability to constantly change with time and not yield to a one size fit all answers. Clarification on this feature of speculation is important as observers and laymen need to be guided that practitioners can respond to situation in the environment in a manner that can change their earlier position on the same subject matter and what can be responsible for this development may be the prevailing condition at the moment, the level of developmental sophistication or lack of it at the moment and the needs of the people and society at that particular point in time.

Analysis as a method of carrying out philosophical research focuses on critically examining words, terms, propositions and concepts with the aim of clarifying and making explicit the various meaning that may be associated with such words, terms, propositions and concepts. Phenomenal attention to clarifying and establishing meanings that are associated with words, terms, propositions and concepts is important because such terms, words, propositions and concepts are the instrument that communicate and convey meaning and correspondingly the rightness and wrongness of any meaning is dependent on the quality of analysis that such words, terms, propositions and concepts have been subjected to. To this end, analysis helps in establishing meaning in the appropriate context, clarifies ambiguities, contradictions and absurdities. By illuminating on the above, analysis promotes thoroughness of thoughts and quality of precision, which on their own are instrumental in bringing to the barest minimum the occurrence of such developments as crises, misunderstandings, conflicts and disagreements.

In addition to establishing meaning, analysis as a method of philosophical research pays epical attention to language and its use and Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2020) justify why this is so when they write that “faulty use of language is at the root of all human conflicts, misunderstanding and crises” hence man’s ability to effectively minimize crises and control his environment depends on man’s ability to manipulate language.

Analysis as a method of philosophical research is unique on many fronts; it has potentials to radicalize and revolutionize the world of knowledge, has potentials to skyrocket the intellectual sophistication of persons who demonstrate and practice it as well as serve as a springboard for improving the quality of human relations upon which the national development of states depends. By making the above norms possible in a state, analysis can be said to have the key for supporting and building a culture of social cohesion that has potentials to place man and his institutions on scales where order and stability can maximally prevail. No wonder analysis has become the trending practice in scholarship and academic pursuits all over the world.

Analysis is of two types namely conceptual and linguistic analysis. Conceptual analysis focuses on ascertaining if the meaning that is associated with a concept, term or word represents what that concept, term or word stands for while linguistic analysis focuses on ascertaining whether the meaning that is ascribed to a sentence actually represents or stands for what that sentence should mean.

Prescription as a method of philosophical research focuses on conscious and deliberate attempt to establish criteria or standards for judging values or making prescriptive values judgment. This outlook for understanding prescription is made more explicit by Odour (2010:97), when he writes that “to prescribe is to recommend or to set down as a rule or a guide.” What this translates into in reality is that all the autonomous value statement in the form of recommendations and suggestions from scholars and researchers that target resolving issues that are the focus of a philosophical discourse qualify as prescription. In fact, Nwaokugha (2021:102) calls attention to this when he writes that prescription:

Is achieved in research in the form of a researcher making autonomous values statements on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be resolved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed. In a way, suggestions and recommendations in researches and other forms of writing fall within the frame of reference of prescription.

On the basis of the above, one can say that prescription is at the heart of any study or research that is worth the name because every study focuses on solving, resolving and addressing one problem or the other and prescription is that section of the study that addresses this challenge. Outside what has been said above, scholars and researchers whose area of scholarship is axiology particularly social philosophy ethics, political philosophy and aesthetics may not be on top of their games without prescription.

The choice of philosophical research methodology for this study is justified because every branch of knowledge according to Nwoke and Nwaokugha (2024) benefits from the philosophical reflections, analysis and rigours of thought that philosophical research methodological is known for, development, that bring about intellectual empowerment of scholars in the forms of widening scholars investigate skills, phenomenal and epical expansion of the epistemological territories and frontiers of disciplines as well as the promotion of collaboration among scholars and researchers that has potentials to triggers the breaking of new frontiers of knowledge among other benefits.

An establish tradition about studies that use the philosophical research methodology is to exclusively and robustly discuss in details key area(s) in the study and to this we now turn.

Early Childhood Care and Education

The education industry of many states is in a state where it is constantly changing and in pursuit of this vision, it incorporates a philosophy and a vision where it reflects the latest trends in the social, religious, cultural, economic, political, scientific and technological aspirations and dreams of the people. This vision and dream of the people which education must incorporate aligns with the overall national

development of the people and their state. In its inclination for change, the education industry of many states repositions itself in readiness for accommodating events and developments that can happen in the future, in the same way as it works retrospectively to healing, remedying and correcting many monumental injustices that had occurred in the past. One trending focal flashpoint in education across the globe is the recognition of education and its provision as a right and indeed a fundamental human right of every citizen. This new outlook and vision about education presently tilts towards providing education to the younger ones from the age of zero (0) up to the formal admission of such persons into the primary school, say five years or more depending on policy prescriptions in some states and this vision has become one that every responsible state has keyed into and correspondingly a matter of national and international concern. Providing care, learning or educational experiences to younger ones from age of zero (0) up to formal admission of such person into the primary school in a formal school like setting or in other arrangement as prescribed by law in some state is called early childhood care and education.

Early childhood care and education enjoys a plethora of scholarly attention from scholars and institutions and these scholarly definitions from scholars agree on many fronts and vary on some. The point of agreement especially in the definition of these scholars is that early childhood care and education is any care and learning or educational experiences provided to the younger ones prior to their admission into the primary school. This is the part highlighted by Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:257) when they write that all the definitions associated with early childhood care and education:

Situate the meaning of early childhood care and education as revolving around consciously packaged behaviour modification and behaviours changing arrangements that are targeted first at safeguarding and protecting the infant from harm and danger as well as providing basic and minimal educational instructions to the infants who are yet to be admitted or enrolled into the primary school.

All early childhood care and education institutions across the globe align themselves with achieving core target and through this way push for new trajectories that have potentials to change narratives for the better particularly for the younger ones, their parents and the state as a whole. It is not in doubt and cannot be doubted that consciously enrolling the younger ones into early childhood care and education programmes has potentials to enhance the moral, social, cognitive, linguistic, numeracy, physical, emotional and psychological developments of the younger ones and these in all sincerity and honesty can positively kick-start the personality development of the learner and his educational pursuits on the right tracks. Early childhood care and education institutions exist as intervention agencies that provide decent comfort zones away from homes for the younger ones and through this way provide opportunities for parents of the younger ones to continue to engage in whatever social and economic activities, they have occupied themselves with for their survival. This has a bigger implication for the economy of the states as parents whose younger ones are in early childhood care and education institutions keep contributing their quota to the national economy and national development of their states. This special role of early childhood care and education institutions, according Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:257)

Means that early childhood care and education incorporates social welfare programmes and policies, which at first targets the betterment of the infant or the young in the state and by implication is a social justice mechanism for progressively rewriting the developmental trajectories or narratives of the state and humanity in general... early childhood care and education promises to be the best platform for achieving such inclusive and comprehensive human capacity building, manpower development and national development agenda.

From the above, it is clear that early childhood care and education is a logical step towards not only early childhood development but a progressive platform and human capital development practice that targets engineering welfare, social welfare and intervention measures with potentials to initiating changes in behaviours that can curb and address issues of backwardness, retrogression, misery and poverty among citizens across the globe and correspondingly early childhood care and education serves as a springboard for triggering and stimulating behaviours where the adult generation acts with courage and commitment, bearing in mind that their ability to achieve their developmental aspirations can only be possible if and only if they (the adults) invest adequately in the younger ones who can sustain, continue and translate their dreams into reality for meaningful and genuine national development to take place. In the same way, the social justice and intervention measures that are associated with early childhood care and education programmes and initiatives have potentials to promote economic and personality growth as well as ignite a revolution where there can be progressive attempts at intergenerationally shared responsibility and shared prosperity between present and future generations.

Therefore, early childhood and education programmes anywhere in the world is more of a clarion call and a trigger for a revolution whose mission can align with whatever developmental aspirations of the state in term of achieving and realizing whatever a state desires or aspires its citizens to become. To this end, a state that is desirous of achieving or making such norms as cooperation, patriotism, love for fatherland, environmental conservation and preservation, tolerance, nationalism, show of respect to elders and constituted authority, love, moderation etc part of the training architecture in the minds of its citizens can do so very early in the lives of the citizens of the state using early childhood care and education. In doing so, the state can be working towards achieving the age long biblical injunction in Proverbs chapter 22:6 which says “train a child in a way he should go, and when he is old, he will not turn from it”, and making the above biblical injunction possible in any society or state using early childhood care and education can also be likened to a building infrastructure, symbolizing the society or the state, where the better the foundation, as par the level of sensitization and conscientization of the members of the state at the early stages of their lives, the better the structure, which is the state. This, by implication means that early childhood care and education can function as a trigger and a foundation for deriving information and data that can guide in the formulation and implementation of general policies for the national development of a state and its people.

Such functions as the above especially the raising of curiosity and hope in directions that are supportive of positive human capital development, national development and human capacity building are responsible for the receptive dispositions that the global community demonstrates towards early childhood care and education, a development that has triggered national and international commitments and a corresponding development of robust ideas and investments in early childhood care and education across the world. These national and international attitudes towards early childhood care and education derives justification from the fact that education as a social provision consolidates itself through its inherent features of self-correction that principally translates into reality through the borrowing and domestication of ideas and making such ideas better along the line in its provision. In fact, the upsurge in robust ideas and investments in early childhood care and education provides sound opportunities for states to learn from one another in their desire and commitment to strengthen and improve their early childhood care and education. To this end, many states have redefined, repositioned and rejigged their education generally and early childhood care and education practices in particular and consequently found their rhythms after they have thoroughly studied, analyzed and compared what exists in their own state with what exists in some other states. This means fruitful and diligent comparison of practices in education especially at the early childhood care and education levels can be taken as the soul and foundation of any state’s vision, quest and mission for exploring the benefits of early childhood care and education whose potentials has multiple implications for human capital development, human capacity building and by implications national development of states. In the next section of this study, efforts will be made to diligently compare early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria.

Early Childhood Care and Education in Malaysia and Nigeria: A Comparative Analysis

There are visible indications that the government of Malaysia and that of Nigeria are committed to using early childhood care and education as a dynamic and progressive force for triggering and repositioning the national development of their two states. Individually, each of the states has robust plans for their early childhood care and education and has initiated policies and programmes that align with the developmental aspirations of the individual states for the advancement and empowerment of the people and their state. Interestingly, there are equally visible signs of deep and shallow commitment toward early childhood care and education from the two states and this makes comparison of the policies, programmes and provision of early childhood care and education in the two states a fascinating and interesting topic.

Early childhood care and education in Malaysia is provided for the citizens from ages 0-6 years in two segments namely from 0-4 years and from 5-6 years. According to Taha, Hanafi, Dzainudin, Ibrahim, Yahaya, Ahmad, Masnan, Ramli, Taib, Mustafa, Yassin, Kastari, David and Padmanathan (2020:145), early childhood care and education in Malaysia is handled by two different ministries. Malaysian babies who are aged from 0-4 years, according to Taha et al (2020) are placed in separate centres under the Department of Social Welfare Services, an agency in the Ministry of Women, Family and Community Development where emphasis is on care, mainly surveillance, protection and safety of the child as well as maintaining the growth and development of infants and toddlers in the Malaysian society while infants from 5-6 years of age are placed in separate centres and correspondingly are co-managed by three ministries namely Ministry of Education, Ministry of Rural and Regional Development and the National Unity Department.

The above is acknowledged by Ridza, Ahmad and Vadeveloo (2024:63) when they write that early childhood care and education in Malaysia is separated into two segments: childcare and preschool. Childcare institutions or centres according to them cater for children from birth to four years while preschool institutions or centres cater for children from five to six years.

Organizationally, there are government-run non-profit early childhood care and education centres, which are mainly located in rural and sub-urban areas that focus more on developing the socio-emotional intelligence of the young ones and non-government for free centres that are mainly found in urban areas and at the same time place a lot of emphasis on the academic development of the young ones. It is important we point out that government funded early childhood care and education centres in Malaysia are free and strictly adhere to the standard national curriculum as well as maintain Malay as their medium of instruction. On the other hand, there are equally private investors, and as private investors, they charge fees for registration, may be at liberty to choose their own medium of instruction as well as introduce and implement their own curriculum (Taha et al, 2020) but must mandatorily and compulsorily implement the national curriculum. The above revelation points in the direction that early childhood care and education in Malaysia is flexible and its flexibility is receptive to making rooms for the introduction of new ideas, innovations and creativity especially from the private investors.

Whether a Malaysian attends a government funded early childhood care and education institution or one that is provided by the private investors, one common denominator that both target to achieve is a holistic upbringing and a holistic education that targets integrating the Malaysian into becoming physically, cognitively, emotionally, linguistically, spiritually, culturally, religiously, hygienically, and socially alert so as to explore and exploit opportunities including acquiring skills for adapting to the demands of an ever-changing twenty-first century environment.

Early childhood care and education is provided for Nigerians from the ages of 0-5 years prior to the official admission of the young Nigerian into the primary school. In Nigeria, early childhood care and education as a provision for the young Nigerian starts from the age of 0-5 years and is subdivided into two parts namely care and education, where care is the starting point and involves what Nwaokugha and Nwogu (2024:66) call “surveillance of the adult over the younger person for the reasons of providing security, protection and keeping the younger one safe from harm and danger”. Because ages 0-3 for Nigeria is dedicated to care, this phase is custodial in nature. Education within the frame of reference of early childhood care and education especially from ages 4-5 focuses on developing the younger one’s

receptive abilities for rudimentary learnings that are supportive of higher order activities such as creative and critical thinking skills that can enhance a smooth transition of the younger one into the primary school.

The above aligns with the purpose of early childhood/pre-primary education as listed by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004:11), which includes to:

- a. Effect a smooth transition from the home to the school
- b. Prepare the child for the primary level of education
- c. Provide adequate care and supervision for the children while their parents are at work (on the farms, in the markets, office etc.
- d. Inculcate social norms
- e. Inculcate in the child the spirit of enquiry and creativity through the exploration of nature, the environment, art, music and playing with toys etc.
- f. Develop a sense of cooperation and team spirit
- g. Learn good habits, especially good health habits, and
- h. Teach the rudiments of numbers, letters, colours, shapes, forms etc through play.

Participation in providing early childhood care and education in Nigeria is the exclusive reserve of the private sector or private investors who consider their involvement in rendering this critical and crucial service as business in which the sole aim of their participation in the sector is to make profit and not to render essential service to the people and the state. To this end, access to this foundational and critical level of human capital development and human capacity building is one that mainly the rich in Nigeria can afford, meaning that majority of Nigerians may not have access to early childhood care and education due to poverty, especially against the background that Nigeria is epically, monumentally and phenomenally poor in the midst of abundant human and natural resource that God lavishly and generously bequeaths to Nigeria. This lopsidedness in access to early childhood care and education in Nigeria has implications for Nigeria's national development and the use of early childhood care and education as a progressive, revolutionary and dynamic policy direction for addressing issues of equity, equality, marginalization, equal educational opportunity, deprivation, justice, human rights and social justice. Following the above remarks, particularly the attitudes of the Nigerian state towards early childhood care and education, one can join issues with Asodike and Abdulrahman (2013:345), who write that:

Issue related to early childhood education in Nigeria at present is not appreciated as a national responsibility. There is no gain saying the fact that government has not demonstrated a serious commitment to education of children between the ages of 0-3 and 3-5 years.

The above is a preamble and correspondingly an insight on the two countries that are the focus of this study as it concerns early childhood care and education and any careful and insightful observer can observe that there are visible similarities and notable differences in the attitudes and dispositions of the governments of the the two countries towards early childhood care and education. In fact, Malaysia and Nigeria are two countries of the world that hold early childhood care and education in high esteem as a foundation and pillar for addressing their historical, cultural, social, economic, civic and political problems of their various states. Interestingly their commitments in this direction reveal common features and epical monumental differences.

A notable similarity in the attitude of Malaysia and Nigeria towards early childhood care and education is that both countries have receptive attitudes that demonstrate their high regard and place of honour for early childhood care and education as a radical and revolutionary trigger for any meaningful human capital development upon which the dreams of national development of both countries can be based. This line of reasoning can be said to derive from their strong beliefs that investments in the younger ones of the two countries, who will further invest in the younger ones of the state in the future is the gateway for achieving whatever developmental aspirations of the two states. In fact, this belief strongly aligns with the position of Eboh (1998) who maintains that human beings are the carriers of the genes that translate into

developments. Early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria share similarities in the area of involvement and participation of the private sector or private investors and on the basis of this the involvement of the private sector or private investor in early childhood care and education and investment in it is a business destination that promises investors phenomenal returns on their investments.

Early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria share similarities in division into two where one is devoted to care while the other is devoted to providing rudimentary learning and educational experiences. Early childhood care and education in both Malaysia and Nigeria is similar in going by different names but its focus is on addressing one social issue namely providing care, learning and educational experiences to the younger ones.

A common denominator which early childhood care and education shares in Malaysia and Nigeria is the limitation and restriction of access to citizens due to its high cost. It is an open secret that the private investors dominate in the provision of early childhood care and education to the citizens of Malaysia and Nigeria (Ridza et al, 2024:64, Rahmatulla, Rawai, Samuri & Yassin, 2021) as their participation is an investment for making gains. What has followed this is that access to early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria has become an essential and elitist commodity that mainly the rich can afford.

In both Malaysia and Nigeria, investors who are interested to operate institution based childcare centres must register such institutions with the appropriate agency of the state. In both Malaysia and Nigeria, the quality of teachers in early childhood care and education institutions and centres are still questionable but Malaysia has some ray of hope than Nigeria in terms of improving teacher quality in early childhood centres as it has made conscious drives to improve the quality of teachers in her early childhood care and education centres. Malaysia has a policy that introduced what Ridza et al (2024:64) call minimum qualification requirements for all pre-school teachers in Malaysia that makes it compulsory for all pre-school teachers in Malaysia to hold at least a Diploma in Early Childhood Education. This conscious move at least as a policy statement is to peg a minimum qualification for teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions and centres. In Nigeria such conscious policy statement has not been initiated or made a priority. The case in Nigeria is graphically highlighted by Nwaokugha (2015:79) when he writes that:

What obtains is that those who aspire to teach is employed by the management or proprietor and most private schools (early childhood care and education centres) in this category have become goldmines and employment destinations for candidates who claim they attended universities or any post -secondary educational institutions but never had certificates. In some cases, holders of questionable secondary school certificates are employed as teachers.

It has to be said with emphasis that there is a lackadaisical attitude and a monumental neglect of early childhood care and education in Nigeria and this monumental neglect begins with the teacher and teacher quality in early childhood care and education institutions across Nigeria. Attention has been called to this by Nwaokugha and Nwogu (2024:70) in these words:

As a sector of education that is operated by the private investors whose sole interests is profit maximization, such investors hardly deem it necessary and essential to recruit the right calibre of teacher who can lay the right foundations at this formative, delicate and critical level of education that is determinant on determining the life of the learner and the future of his state. What has become the norm in early childhood care and education in Nigeria is a situation where there is acute lack of qualified teachers and the profit minded orientation and capitalist inclinations of the private sector make them to capitalize on profit maximization as against employing capable and qualified teachers into their establishments.

What has come to be the norm about early childhood care and education in Nigeria is that a reasonable number of such centres and institutions exist in buildings and structures that originally and purposefully were not built for educational purposes and majority exist without registration and official approval including terribly and disastrously coming short of the serenity that can pop up and stimulate the intellectual curiosity that can challenge a learner to learn. In a way, early childhood care and education in Nigeria is under the inglorious tight grips of the general lip service that education generally suffers in Nigeria. Nigerians are yet to correspond the declaration of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004:11) with reality that government shall:

- (a) Establish pre-primary sections in existing schools and encourage both community/private efforts in the provision of pre-primary education
- (b) Make provision in teacher education programmes for specialization in early childhood education
- (c) Ensure that the medium of instruction is principally the mother tongue or language of the immediate community.

It is correct to say that the attitudes and commitments of governments and individuals in both Malaysia and Nigeria marks a sensitive turning point in the commitment of Malaysia and Nigeria towards early childhood care education in both countries. In Malaysia, there are different classes of childhood care centres namely (a) community childcare centres (b) workplace childcare centres (c) institution based, and (d) home based childcare centres and a thing of interest about them is that the federal and state governments provide incentives to the operators of such centres. According to Rahmatullah et al (2021), community childcare centres in Malaysia receives assistance from the Federal and State Governments when they care for ten or more children and a 10% tax reduction for ten years of operation is provided or offered to workplace childcare centres. In Malaysia, there are other classes of people who provide preschools and, in their mission, and vision target children from families with low incomes and localities that maintain friendly neighborhood schemes. This suggests that there is a combination of coded public and private participation in making available early childhood care and education to Malaysians especially when it has been noted that government allocates substantial amount of fund for early childhood care and education institutions and centres every year. Governments in Nigeria do not provide any incentive or moral boost to organizations, individuals or institutions that provide childcare services to Nigerians unlike the way it is done in Maylaysia. The involvement of Nigerian government on record concerning early childhood care and education is this declaration that:

The responsibility of government for pre-primary education shall be to promote the training of qualified pre-primary school teachers in adequate member, contribute to the development of suitable curriculum, supervise and control the quality of such institutions and establish pre-primary sections in existing public schools (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004:11)

CONCLUSION

Scholars who show interests in comparative studies especially in education target many things at the same time ranging from comparing educational systems across states, studying social developments particularly how political, cultural, religious, environmental and economic conditions of a people shape, determine and influence educational developments, highlight how events and happenings in one state can be a trigger for modeling, transforming and translating the positive developments in the education system of another state into reality, create insights in individuals and states on how to resolve and address educational challenges from the experiences of states that have overcome their educational challenges especially when such states share similar educational, social, political, economic and cultural experiences and peculiarities or put slightly different to under study states that share the same social, environmental, political, economic and cultural characteristics with another state or with one's own state but have robustly and gallantly overcome such challenges to the point of becoming global role models in the quality of education, human capital and capacity building such states offer to their people. This points in

the direction that only a scholar who shows interests in comparative studies especially in education may be highlighting aspects of educational provisions and experiences in two or more countries of his choice with a view to creating insight or awareness on them vis-à-vis what exist somewhere else. This study has focused on comparative analysis of early childhood care and education in Malaysia and Nigeria.

Malaysia and Nigeria can be said to be two states that recognize the creative and critical roles of early childhood care and education in helping their individual states build a formidable, strong and prosperous state of their dreams as both states share some striking similarities as well as wide differences in their devotion and commitment to providing their citizens with quality and robust early childhood care and education. The truth must be said without fear or favour that there are areas where each of the two states can be scored higher or lower in the assessment of their devotion and commitment to early childhood care and education in their respective states. The organization, focus, priority and commitment of Malaysia to early childhood care and education is appreciable and correspondingly a demonstration of action and political will of a state that is determined to launch itself to the next level of development through conscious efforts that target exploring all those inherent benefits that are associated with early childhood care and education and this is demonstrated in Malaysia's conscious and well-coordinated investments in raising a generation of young persons who can be educationally curious to acquire skills and knowledge for translating the developmental aspirations of the adults of today into reality. To this end, Malaysia may experience general exponential development and transformation if it sustains its present commitment and investment in early childhood care and education.

Nigeria on the other hand is a country that is known for its lip services to serious national issues including those like early childhood care and education that have potentials to skyrocket Nigeria's drive and aspirations for national development. Lip services that Nigeria is known for show itself in Nigeria's decision to domicile the provision of early childhood care and education in the hands of the private investors only with Nigeria's responsibility being "to promote the training of qualified pre-primary teachers in adequate number, contribute to the development of suitable curriculum, supervise and control the quality of such constitutions". This declaration calls for adequate scrutiny in terms of ascertaining the number of teacher education institutions or faculty of Education in Universities that have Department of Early Childhood Care and Education so as to translate the training of qualified pre-primary teachers into reality and the possibility that Nigeria in her present attitude can exercise and demonstrate the right quality assurance and oversight functions as it claims without compromise. The neglect of this fundamental and foundational segment of education in Nigeria may be pointing in the direction that Nigeria's dream of quality human capital development and human capacity building that can effectively trigger Nigeria's national development may still be a distant dream and correspondingly Nigeria can be said to be performing abysmally below average in terms of policy initiatives and actions that target raising a generation of learners in the early childhood care and education institutions that can successfully and existentially take over from the present generation of elders.

All said and done, both Malaysia and Nigeria can still initiate conscious efforts so as to consolidate whatever has been achieved before and move forward or alternatively consciously ignite radical revolutions that can lay foundations for effective and successful plans for the robust and receptive take off of actions, policies and political will that can reposition, recognize and prioritize the importance of early childhood care and education in the developmental drives of the two states. Specifically, the government of Malaysia in its bold and landmark achievements in early childhood care childhood care and education can double its incentives to private investors in her early childhood care and education institutions and at the same time increase its participation in the sector. Those private investors should be encouraged to introduce into the system those their entrepreneurial skills that stand them out, as through this way, there can be quality competitions that can enhance the quality of service which Malaysia government and the private investors provide.

On the part of Nigeria, efforts should be made to establish early childhood care and education departments in all teacher education institutions in Nigeria to help translate into reality the aspiration of promoting the training of qualified preprimary school teachers. The government of Nigeria should as a

matter of national interest and national responsibility take active part in providing early childhood care and education to Nigerians through operating and owning early childhood care and education institutions or centres or alternatively the structure of the education system in Nigeria may be said to be hanging or incomplete due to the neglect and non-involvement of the government at this fundamental and foundational level of education. The Federal Government of Nigeria should modify and re-strategize in terms of conducting its oversight functions on early childhood care and education institutions in the country. The private investors in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria should be allowed to introduce cutting edge entrepreneurial innovations that can serve as foundations for their uniqueness and basis upon which they can enjoy some patronage from Nigerians as the more innovations, the more competitions that can be for the benefit, satisfaction and national development of the Nigerian state. Lastly, the private investors who invest in early childhood care and education in Nigeria are providing critical, fundamental and foundational services that the Nigerian state ought to constitutionally and statutorily provide and correspondingly deserve some compensation for it. To this end, the government of Nigeria should think along the line of providing incentives for them and stop or have a rethink on the habit of over taxing such investors.

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